

CHOOSE : COMPOSITION OR INHERITANCE .

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ANNOTATION

This article shows the choice of composition or inheritance method in JAVA programming language. Issues for applying these methods and of issues the solution given

Keywords: class, public, final

ANNOTATION

This article shows the choice of composition or inheritance method in JAVA programming language. Problems and solutions to problems are given for the application of these methods

Keywords: class, public, final

In general, composition is used when you need to access the properties of an existing class in your class, not its interface.

In inheritance while there is class taken from him another specialized class is made . Of this for common responsible class is applied and special task for will be changed . on the moon of inheritance necessary despite design initial in steps from the composition use better because _ this style more flexible than inheritance while objective in necessity use need _

```
class Engine {  
    public void Start ( ) {}  
    public void rev ( ) {}  
    public void stop ( ) {}  
}  
class Wheel {  
    public void inflate ( int psi) {}  
}  
class Window  
    public void rollup ( ) {}  
    public void rolldown ( ) {}  
}  
class Door {  
    public Window Window = new Window ( );
```



```

public void open () {}
public void close () {}
}
public class Car {
public Engine engine = new Engine ();
public Wheel [] = new Wheel [ 4 ];
public Door left = new Door ();
right = new Door ();
Car () {
for ( int i = 0; i < 4; i ++ )
Wheel [ i ] = new Wheel ();
}
public static void main (String args [ ]) {
Car car = new Car ();
Car. Left. Window. rollup ();
Car. Wheel [0]. inflate (72); }}

```

The final key the word

This is the word change the meaning to « possible understand that " not ". can _ You changes two without your permission can : Efficiency increase and second design . Final variable (dates), style and class to be can _ final variable (class information compilers). Programming a lot languages to the compiler of the program which one piece constant that to say possibility will be Constantly of information two type available : compilation on time constant (none when does not change) and program work on time to be initialized constant . Simple ones final word for simple the meaning immutable does _ But pointers for this concept little difference does _ final pointer constant does _ That's why for pointer his announcement to be done on time initialized to be need and this the pointer is pointing to it object change it ca n't But of the object its meanings _ change it takes _

```

class Value {
int i = i;
}
public class FinalData {
finalint i 1= 9;
static finalint 12 = vv
public static final int 13 = 3 v
final int I 4 = ( int ) (Math. random ( ) * 20);

```



```

static final int i 5 = ( int ) (Math. random ( ) * 20);
Value v 1 = new Value ( );
static final Value v 3 = new Value ( );
//! final Value v 4 , // 1 1 in java error initialization load _
// Arrays :
final int [ ] a = {1,2,3,4,5,6};
public void print(String id) {
System. out . println (
id + « : » + « i 4 » + , « i 5 = » + i 5);
}
public static void main ( String [ ] args ) {
Final Data fd 1 = new Final Data ( );
//! fd 1 . i 1 + + ; // error : meaning by changing can't .
fd 1 . v 2 . + + ; // . A constant object .
fd 1 . v 1 = new Value ( ); // This can _
for ( int i = 0 , i < fd 1 . a length ; i + + )
fd 1 . a [ i ] + + ; // This can _
//! fd 1 . v 2 = new Value ( ) , // error : possible not _
//! fd 1 . v 3 = new Value ( ) , // sent change _
//! fd 1 . a = new int [ 3 ];
fd 1 . print ( " fd 1 " );
System. out . println ( " Creating new Final Data " );
Final Data fd 2 = new Final Data ( );
fd 1 . print ( " fd 1 " );
fd 1 . print ( " fd 1 " );
}
} //! : ~
final styles .

```

As a final determined styles to you apply necessary of being two reason there is the first is style in such " closed " inheritance his the meaning never who change it do not take and the second is the program efficiency increase _ final the key of the word main meaning the same final dec to variables .

A gar style parameters as final determined if it is so you style inside this to the variable new meaning give you ca n't

```

class gizmo {
public void spring ( ) {}
}

```



```
public class FinalArguments {
void with (final gizmo g) {
//! g = new gizmo (); // possible not g-final
g. sprint ( );
}
g
g. sprint ( );
}
// void f ( final int i ) { i + + ; } // replacement possible it's not .
int g ( final int i ) { return i + 1; }
public static void main ( string [ ] args ) {
Final Arguments ff = new FinalArguments ( );
ff. with . out ( null );
ff. with ( null );
}
}
```

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